

APPENDICES

Appendix I: Questionnaire to credit officers and credit customers

Dear Respondent

I am Sewanyina Muniru, PhD student undertaking research on “Corporate Governance Practices and Non-Performing Loans of Commercial Banks in Greater Bushenyi Districts.” The information sought is required for academic purposes only. Your participation in this study is voluntary but necessary for the success of this work. I request you to agree to participate in this study for the success of the research. Confidentiality will be ensured for information provided by ensuring anonymity.

Sincerely

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Muniru Sewanyina

SECTION A: Background Characteristics

Tick in the appropriate place provided

1. My Gender

Male	Female

2. My age group

emyaka 20-29	emyaka 30-39	emyaka 40-49	emyaka 50 n'okukiraho

3. My highest level of education attained

Diplomas	Bachelor's Degree	Master Degree and above

4. I have worked or dealt in/with this Bank for

Less than 5 years old	5 - 10 years	11 years and above

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5. The responsibility I hold in this bank

Board member	General Manager	Employee	the client

Section B: Non-Performing Loans (DV)

This section presents items on non-performing loans. You are kindly requested to indicate the extent to which you exhibit the performance herein using the scale where, 1 = Never, 2 = Rarely, 3 = Sometimes, 4 = Often and 5 = Always

	Statements			3	2	1
1	Restructuring procedures require a relatively long period of time before achieving recovery					
2	Liquidations and restructurings vary in duration and in the average share of loans backed by guarantees					
3	Non-performing loans are mainly managed through transfers to third parties or by special internal units.					
4	Banks' organizational structures for managing non-performing loans appear to be diversified.					
5	The significant impact of managing non-performing loans on banks' costs is also affected by the lack of efficiency of legal procedures.					
6	Banks pointed out that the main obstacles to efficient credit recovery are the backlogs in the courts and the complexity of procedures.					
7	There are professional fees and difficulties in coordinating with non-financial creditors					

	Most of the loans are guaranteed with valuable items				3	2	1
9	Our bank is managed and run by professionals with high integrity						
10	There is thorough assessment of clients before giving out loans						

Section C: Corporate Governance practices

C1	Board Accountability	5	4	3	2	1	
1	Board members are subject to annual election by all shareholders						
2	Non-executive board members have a formal session without executives once a year						
3	The Company discloses a code of ethics for senior executives						
4	The Company discloses its corporate governance policies or guidelines						
5	The board or a committee is responsible for CEO succession planning						
6	The Company has not failed to adopt the recommendations of a shareholder proposal						
7	All executive board members hold their own shares after excluding options						
8	All non-executive board members hold their own shares after excluding options						
9	The Company has a separate chairman and CEO						
10	All members attended at least 75% of the board meetings						
C2	Financial Disclosure	5	4	3	2	1	
1	Our bank prepares clear, concise financial statements in accordance with relevant accounting standards						

2	Our bank discloses its financial policies for evaluating assets and liabilities					
3	Our bank provides comprehensive and meaningful notes to explain the numbers presented in financial statements					
4	The Company is not currently under investigation for accounting irregularities					
5	Our bank practice segment reporting to show the performance of different segments					
6	There is transparency in disclosing transactions in our bank.					
7	There is timely reporting in our bank					
8	The management discussion and analysis section is catered for in the preparation of financial reports					
C3	Shareholders' Rights	5	4	3	2	1
1	Voting results for the last shareholder meeting are disclosed within 14 calendar days					
2	All common or ordinary equity shares have one share, one vote, with no restrictions					
3	The Company provides confidential voting with no or without reasonable exception					
4	Shareholders have the right to convene an EGM with 10% or less of the shares requesting one					
5	Shareowners have the right to act in concert through written communication					
6	There is equal treatment of all shareholders of the bank					
7	Shareholders participate in the approval of major transactions					
8	Shareholders have received dividends as per bank policy					
9	Shareholders are given the right to nominate directors					
10	The shareholders are given the right to request additional information and clarity from the bank					
C4	Remuneration	5	4	3	2	1

1	There is independence of the compensation committee from the directors					
2	The Bank normally discloses the compensation policy to shareholders					
3	There is a mixture of board compensation components.					
4	The bank has put in place equity ownership guidelines to determine who should be a director in terms of number of shares					
5	Goals used to determine incentive awards are aligned with the Company's financial goals					
6	The CEO/Managing Director does not sit on the remuneration committee					
7	The remuneration committee is composed wholly of independent board members					
8	The bank operates performance-based compensation when renumbering directors					
9	Additional compensation is normally provided to directors who chair key board committees					
10	The board members normally receive an annual retainer for their services rendered					
C5	Interest rates					
C						
1	Our bank Interest rates are reasonable					
2	Our bank charge different interest rate					
3	The interest rate of our bank remains fixed throughout the loan period					
4	I am informed by the bank the prevailing interest rates of different loans before borrowing					
5	I am kept in the loop by my supervisor about the interest rates					
6	I am finding difficulties in paying the interest charged on the loan					
7	I am rewarded/recognized whenever I pay the loan principal and interest rates on time					

8	I am willing to share the benefits I got from paying my loan on time					
9	I believe the loan department listens to my suggestions on the interest rates					
10	I can arrange my payment schedule to meet my loan repayment targets					

Appendix II: Interview Guide for Board representatives and Bank Managers

Dear Respondent

I am Sewanyina Muniru, PhD student undertaking research on “Corporate Governance Practices and Non-Performing Loans of Commercial Banks in Greater Bushenyi Districts.” The information sought is required for academic purposes only. Your participation in this study is voluntary but necessary for the success of this work. I request you to agree to participate in this study for the success of the research. Confidentiality will be ensured for information provided by ensuring anonymity.

Sincerely

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Muniru Sewanyina

Board Accountability and Non-Performing Loans of Commercial Banks in Greater Bushenyi Districts

1. In your opinion, to what extent does the board interfere or help the bank to solve the problem of non-performing loans
2. How would banks manage non-performing loans?
3. How often does the board sit to discuss issues related to non-performing loans?

Financial Transparency and Non-Performing Loans of Commercial Banks in Greater Bushenyi Districts

1. What kind of internal control has the board instituted to prevent and solve the problem of non-performing loans
2. In your opinion, do you think there is transparency in giving out loans to the clients? If yes, how?
3. What efforts have the board put in place to ensure that the internal controls in relation to issuing loans are sound and effective

Shareholders' Rights and Non-Performing Loans of Commercial Banks in Greater Bushenyi Districts.

1. In your opinion, do you think shareholders of your bank are given a chance to give suggestions on how to handle non-performing loans
2. To what extent has the shareholders influenced the issue of non-performing loans in your bank
3. How to resolve non-performing loans through data-driven digital experiences

Board Compensation and Non-Performing Loans of Commercial Banks in Greater Bushenyi Districts.

1. How do you normally compute the remuneration of the board members?
2. In your opinion, do you think remuneration of board of directors has any impact on non-performing loans of commercial banks
3. What challenges is the board facing in handling the non-performing loans

Interest Rate and Non-Performing Loans of Commercial Banks in Greater Bushenyi Districts.

1. Does the board of directors have any influence in fixing the interest rates of the bank?
2. In your opinion, do you think interest rates affect the non-performing loans of commercial banks?
3. What problems do you think your clients are facing when paying bank, the loans and their associated interest?

Thanks, you for your cooperation